

Black Holes/Singularities are responsible for Universal Expansion/Dark Energy

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Abstract: Black Holes cause a 'pressure' difference when consuming mass, causing Universal expansion and dark energy.

Starting with 3 points:

- (1) Universal expansion speed is increasing,
- (2) Primordial blackholes have existed since the beginning of the universe.
- (3) Expelling mass causes movement.

The Dirac equation and Pauli exclusion principle appear to state that no two particles can occupy the same place in space-time. However, in a singularity, this appears contradicted. But since singularities exist, it is not.

The answer is close to pressure. As a black hole consumes matter, to resist violating the principle, the matter must be stored somewhere else outside of space-time. If this matter is temporary stored outside of space-time, then space must compensate by stretching around the black hole in all directions. This is a pressure blowback from the forced storage outside local space-time. It is the equal and opposite reaction to throwing matter one direction (outside the Universe). This is shown by the conservation of energy and the fact that mass can be converted to energy. When this matter is 'thrown' outside the Universe, its reverse momentum causes universal stretching. Since hardly any black holes have burned out, this matter is still technically cached causing an additive effect on acceleration of galaxies over time.

Additionally, the clustering of blackholes, which would be higher closer to the center of the universe, makes this stretching appear more extreme and cause greater acceleration on the edge of the Universe, due to the summations of the stretching/force in the directions of each other helping to cancel out this effect in the local region, along with the gravity of the singularities themselves.

Over time, as singularities evaporate, the acceleration will slow.